

Factsheet

The main NBS to be tested in the UK involve diversifying arable rotations and using bio-based fertilisers, in particular: (1) Crop rotations and use of cover crops and green manure; (2) Farmyard manure (P) applications efficiency; (3) Recycled fertiliser made from abattoir by-products (primarily bones) as a source of phosphorus.

Funded by the European Union

trans4num is a four-year project funded under the Zero Pollution call as an EU-China international cooperation action on nature-based solutions (NBS) for nutrient management in agriculture.

trans4num ambition is to broadly enhance the NBS implementation in Europe with an integrative and tested multi-level approach, in dialogue with academic partners, practice partners and societal stakeholders.

<http://trans4num.eu>